

Hydrogen purification for fuel cells : selective oxidation of carbon monoxide on Pd and FePd/Al₂O₃ catalysts^ψ

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γ-Alumina supported Pd and Pd-based bimetallic catalysts were tested for selective oxidation of carbon monoxide in the presence of excess hydrogen (SELOX). The catalysts were prepared by the incipient wetness impregnation technique, and were studied in the temperature range between 40 and 250°C. The activity of the 15%Pd-2.5%Fe catalyst was found to be better than the Pd-only catalyst, especially in the temperature range, 90-165°C. Increasing the Fe content further decreased the activity of the catalyst. Pre-reductive treatments given to the 5%Pd-2.5%Fe promoted catalyst resulted in a catalyst showing better performance at temperatures below 100°C.

Spurred on by the promise of significantly higher efficiency and almost no emission of pollutants, proton exchange membrane fuel cells (PEMFCs) have been extensively studied in the last two decades for many applications especially for low emission vehicles¹⁻⁴. Ideally, PEMFCs require pure hydrogen as fuel. However presently, there is no available technology for safe on-board storage of hydrogen to give a PEMFC powered vehicle an acceptable range. It is known that hydrogen can be supplied on-demand by various methods; for example, steam reforming of methanol or other liquid hydrocarbon fuels in a fuel processor and so on. When hydrogen is produced via the reforming reaction, the gas always contains CO as a poisoning impurity. Therefore, the hydrogen production system must be equipped with a CO removal system. Although CO concentration can be decreased via the water-gas shift reaction, the product stream usually contains about 1-2 vol% CO. This is because the water-gas shift reaction is a reversible reaction, and CO cannot be removed completely. Many studies have shown the negative effect of CO on the performance of PEM fuel cell^{5,6}. Palladium-based membrane purification, catalytic methanation, and selective catalytic CO oxidation are the methods of reducing the CO in the feed stream to the levels necessary for operation of the fuel cell, with minimal loss of hydrogen. Of these three methods, the selective CO oxidation (SELOX) method is the most promising and lowest cost approach. However, hydrogen oxida-

tion competes with CO oxidation leading to the loss of fuel efficiency. In order to reduce CO to the desired level and to minimize H₂ oxidation, selective and active catalysts are needed. In order to remove CO selectively from the hydrogen stream, the catalytic oxidation of CO has been carried out by use of various supported Pt⁷, Au⁸ and Cu⁹ catalysts.

Purifying H₂ by selectively oxidizing trace amounts of CO by catalytic oxidation over a noble-metal-based catalyst is not new. The first patent for selectively oxidizing CO in hydrogen by a Pt/alumina catalyst was awarded to Engelhard in 1963¹⁰. Oh and Sinkevitch studied the selectivity and activity of alumina-supported Pt, Pd, Ru and Rh with a gas stream containing CO, O₂ and H₂¹¹.

Although the high activity of Pt, Ir and Pd has been reported towards CO oxidation reaction under oxygen-lean conditions in three-way catalysis¹²⁻¹⁴, but selective oxidation of CO in presence of hydrogen over Pd does not appear to have been studied. The present study was initiated with the thought that some analogies could be found with the SELOX reaction by employing Pd and Pd-based bimetallic catalysts. Palladium on different supports is a well-known oxidation catalyst, on which the chemisorbed CO reacts with the subsurface oxygen. Since the bimetallic catalysts are known to show better catalytic activity (and/or selectivity) and higher resistance to deactivation as compared to the monometallic catalysts,

^ψDedicated to Professor H. C. Gaur on his 80th birthday.

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an attempt has been made to study the effect of the addition of iron towards the CO oxidation activity in the presence of a large excess of hydrogen over Pd/ γ -Al₂O₃ catalyst.

Results and discussion

Approximately 50 mg of each catalyst were used for the selective oxidation experiment. The reaction gas feed used for the present study contained 1.25% O₂, 0.50% CO, ~25% H₂ and balance N₂. The catalysts were exposed to the reaction gas mixture for approximately 20 min before the tests. Since there was no water present in the gaseous feedstock, the experiments were essentially dry CO tests. The reaction gas feed did not contain CO₂ due to the interference with O₂ measurements. The total flow rate of the reaction gas was maintained at 200 cm³ min⁻¹. The reaction products were analyzed using a gas chromatograph (Ai Cambridge GC 94) fitted with a TCD with Molecular Sieve 5A 100–120 mesh. A CO₂ sensor (Servomex Analyzer Series 1400) was also used to analyze the amount of CO₂ in the output. This provided us with an effective way to crosscheck the CO consumption monitored on the GC and the CO₂ formed during the tests on the CO₂ sensor. Calibration of the CO₂ sensor with respect to the GC, using a calibration gas mixture and also the gas mixture used for the CO tests, gave very consistent results. The amount of CO consumed, as analyzed by GC, was in good agreement with that shown on the CO₂ sensor.

The term '%Conversion' is defined as

$$\% \text{Conversion} = \frac{\text{CO (or O}_2\text{) consumed}}{\text{Total CO (or O}_2\text{) in the gas mixture}} \times 100\%$$

The term selectivity of a catalyst towards CO oxidation ($S(\text{CO})$) is defined as follows :

$$S(\text{CO}) = \frac{\text{Amount of O}_2 \text{ consumed}}{\text{Total amount of O}_2 \text{ in the gas mixture}} \times 100\%$$

As neither H₂ nor H₂O concentrations were measured in the experiment, the hydrogen selectivity ($S(\text{H}_2)$) was calculated on the assumption that any difference between O₂ and CO consumptions can be accounted for by H₂ oxidation.

5%Pd/Al₂O₃ Catalyst - calcined at 450°C for 5 h :

When the gas mixture containing 1.25% O₂, 0.50% CO, ~25% H₂ and balance N₂, was passed over the

5%Pd/Al₂O₃ catalyst, low activity (< 5%) was observed at ~45°C (Fig. 1). By 70°C, only about 10% CO was oxidised over the catalyst. A gradual increase in CO conversion to ~20% was observed when the temperature of the catalyst was raised to 116°C. 50% CO was converted to CO₂ at 157°C. The maximum amount of CO that was found to be oxidised under the present conditions was approximately 65% at 194°C over the 5%Pd/Al₂O₃ catalyst. Further increase in temperature resulted in a slight decrease of CO conversion to ~60% towards the end of the experiment. Oxygen was observed to be consumed quickly in the reaction suggesting either a rapid uptake by the catalyst, or that it has been used for hydrogen oxidation.

Fig. 1. CO conversion, O₂ consumed and selectivity profiles for 5% Pd/Al₂O₃ catalyst calcined at 450°C for 5 h, as a function of temperature.

5%Pd-2.5%Fe/Al₂O₃ Catalyst - calcined at 450°C for 5 h :

The selective oxidation of CO in the presence of hydrogen using 5%Pd-2.5%Fe/ γ -Al₂O₃ exhibited low activity at the beginning of experiment (Fig. 2). Less than 10% CO was found to be oxidized until 75°C. With the rise in temperature, CO conversion started to increase and showed 50% CO conversion at 137°C. Once again the consumption of oxygen was found to be faster than CO oxidation. The CO conversion seemed to slow down at ~160°C after oxidising approximately 62% CO to CO₂ which can be seen as a plateau in the CO oxidation profile in Fig. 2. At ~215°C, CO conversion again started to rise with temperature and the maximum CO conversion that was observed over the 5%Pd-2.5%Fe/Al₂O₃

catalyst was approximately 84% at 233°C.

Fig. 2. CO conversion, O₂ consumed and selectivity profiles for 5%Pd-2.5%Fe/Al₂O₃ catalyst calcined at 450°C for 5 h, as a function of temperature

5%Pd-5%Fe/Al₂O₃ Catalyst – calcined at 450°C for 5 h :

Compared to the other catalysts, better CO conversions were observed over the 5%Pd-5%Fe/Al₂O₃ catalyst (Fig. 3). 10% CO was found to be oxidised at 65°C. A gradual increase in CO conversion was observed with the rise in temperature reaching 20% at 135°C. The consumption of oxygen was again found to be higher than CO conversion. With the rise in temperature, CO conversion increases slowly reaching 50% at 199°C. The maximum CO conversion observed in this case was 82% at 248°C.

Fig. 3. CO conversion, O₂ consumed and selectivity profiles for 5%Pd-5%Fe/Al₂O₃ catalyst calcined at 450°C for 5 h, as a function of temperature.

Fig. 4 shows the profiles for CO oxidation over the 5%Pd, 5%Pd-2.5%Fe and 5%Pd-5%Fe, catalysts as a function of temperature. Addition of Fe to Pd-only systems gave overall higher CO conversions (>80% compared to 64%) as seen from T_{max} values in Table 1. Upon comparing the CO oxidation profiles of the Pd-only catalyst and the (2.5%)Fe-promoted catalyst it is clear that the Fe-promoted catalyst showed improved activity in the temperature range 90–165°C (Fig. 4). Increasing Fe loading in the catalyst to 5% seems to decrease activity of the catalyst. This indicates that probably the addition of excess Fe blocks the active Pd sites for the reaction thereby resulting in slowing down of the CO oxidation. It may be concluded from these observations that there might be an optimum limit of Fe that should be added to Pd catalyst in order to achieve an effective low temperature CO oxidation in presence of hydrogen.

Fig. 4. CO conversion over Pd and promoted Pd catalysts as a function of temperature.

Table 1. The activity-selectivity and related parameters for the catalysts prepared

System	$T(50)/^{\circ}\text{C}$	$S(\text{CO})/\%$	$T_{max}/^{\circ}\text{C}$
5%Pd	157	10	$T_{64} = 194$
5%Pd-2.5%Fe	137	~10	$T_{84} = 233$
5%Pd-5%Fe	199	10	$T_{82} = 248$

T_{max} is the temperature at which maximum CO oxidation was observed.

$T(50)$ is the temperature at which 50% CO oxidation was observed.

$S(\text{CO})$ is the selectivity towards CO oxidation at $T(50)$.

Proposed mechanism :

In addition to the generally accepted Langmuir-Hinshelwood mechanism, there is an additional possibil-

ity that CO is adsorbed on the Pd sites (S_{Pd}) whereas O_2 is adsorbed dissociatively on the surface FeO_x sites (S_{FeO_x}). A surface reaction can then take place between the adjacently adsorbed reactants to give CO_2 which then desorbs as the gaseous product. The sequence of elementary steps in the proposed mechanism is described below.

Reductive treatment :

As shown before, of all the three systems studied 5%Pd-2.5%Fe/ Al_2O_3 showed better performance than the others. Since pre-reductive treatment of the catalysts prior to the CO oxidation is known to enhance the performance of the catalysts, an attempt has been made to study the effect of pre-reduction of 5%Pd-2.5%Fe/ Al_2O_3 catalyst under a 2%CO/ H_2 mixture at 200°C and at 300°C for 40 min.

5%Pd-2.5%Fe/ Al_2O_3 Catalyst - reduced at 200°C for 40 min :

The CO oxidation profile for the 5%Pd-2.5%Fe/ Al_2O_3 catalyst, reduced at 200°C for 40 min, is shown as a function of temperature in Fig. 5. Even after the reduction at 40°C, the 5%Pd-2.5%Fe/ Al_2O_3 catalyst showed low activity converting only 10% CO in the mixture to CO_2 until 90°C. With gradual increase in temperature the CO conversion also increased slowly, reaching 50% level at 147°C. The CO conversion increased with the rise in temperature, reaching the maximum CO conversion, 72%, at 218°C.

Fig. 5. CO conversion, O_2 consumed and selectivity profiles for 5%Pd-2.5%Fe/ Al_2O_3 catalyst reduced at 200°C for 40 min.

5%Pd-2.5%Fe/ Al_2O_3 Catalyst - reduced at 300°C for 40 min :

The CO oxidation profile for the 5%Pd-2.5%Fe/ Al_2O_3 catalyst, reduced at 300°C for 40 min, is shown as a function of temperature in Fig. 6. After the reduction at 300°C, the 5%Pd-2.5%Fe/ Al_2O_3 catalyst showed much improved activity, oxidising 20% CO in the mixture at 85°C. With gradual increase in temperature, the CO conversion also increased, gradually reaching 50% at 100°C. The CO conversion increased with the rise in temperature reaching the maximum CO conversion of 60% at 243°C.

Fig. 6. CO conversion, O_2 consumed and selectivity profiles for 5%Pd-2.5%Fe/ Al_2O_3 catalyst reduced at 300°C for 40 min.

Comparative %CO conversion graphs have been plotted (Fig. 7) and Table 2 summarises the comparative data for the 5%Pd-2.5%Fe/ Al_2O_3 catalysts that were reduced at 200°C and 300°C for 40 min prior to the CO oxidation test. It is clear that reduction at 200°C yielded a slightly more active catalyst (converted 72% CO compared to 64% for Pd-only catalyst). However, reduction at 300°C resulted in the formation of a catalyst that showed slightly better activity at temperatures below 100°C, and similar activity at higher temperatures. Even after reductive treatments none of the Pd catalysts showed good selectivity towards CO in presence of hydrogen.

Slightly better activity of the reduced Pd/ Al_2O_3 catalysts is similar to the complicated conversion versus temperature profiles previously reported for the methanol and formaldehyde oxidation over Pd/ Al_2O_3 ¹⁵. Better acti-

Fig. 7. CO conversion over 5%Pd–2.5%Fe catalysts after reduction at 200°C and 300°C.

vity at lower temperatures (below 135°C), especially in the case of the catalyst reduced at 300°C, could be attributed to the presence of Pd in a highly active reduced form. With the rise in temperature this reduced Pd is oxidised to PdO_x, a less active form, and hence a slowing down of CO conversion. It seems some more fine tuning of the reaction parameters needs to be done in order to find a suitable catalyst based on Pd.

Experimental

The support, γ -Al₂O₃, was received in the form of cylindrical pellets, which were crushed to a grain size of 250–500 μ m range with a surface area of \sim 190 m² g⁻¹. The bimetallic Fe–Pd catalysts were prepared by successive impregnation. Incipient wetness impregnation was followed for the preparation of 2% and 5%Pd on γ -Al₂O₃ with a solution of palladium acetylacetonate in toluene. The catalyst was dried and in the second step, the resulting Pd/ γ -Al₂O₃ catalyst was impregnated with ferrocene (Fe(C₅H₅)₂) solution.

After the second impregnation step, the catalysts were dried and calcined at 450°C for 5 h. The following catalysts were prepared :

- 5%Pd/Al₂O₃
- 5%Pd–2.5%Fe/Al₂O₃
- 5%Pd–5%Fe/Al₂O₃

Table 2. The activity-selectivity and related parameters for the reduced 5%Pd–2.5%Fe/Al₂O₃ catalyst

Catalyst	Treatment	T(50)/ °C	S(CO)/ %	T _{max} / °C
5%Pd/Al ₂ O ₃	–	157	10	T ₆₄ = 194
5%Pd–2.5%Fe/Al ₂ O ₃	200°C–40 min	147	10	T ₇₂ = 218
5%Pd–2.5%Fe/Al ₂ O ₃	300°C–40 min	100	10	T ₆₀ = 243

Conclusions :

Adding 2.5%Fe to the Pd-only catalyst improved the activity of the Pd catalyst but it did not affect the selectivity of the catalyst significantly. Increasing the Fe-content in the catalyst to 5% decreased the CO conversion further. Reductive treatments given to 5%Pd–2.5%Fe/Al₂O₃ catalyst marginally improved the CO conversion; however, reduction at 300°C yielded a catalyst that was more active at lower temperatures (<100°C). A more detailed study of the system could result in the development of a catalyst which is active for the low temperature CO oxidation in presence of hydrogen.

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